

Supplementary materials related to the article "Effects of reverberation on speech intelligibility in noise for hearing-impaired listeners"

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This document contains the supplementary materials
for the study "Effects of reverberation on speech
intelligibility in noise for hearing-impaired listeners". The
following elements are included:

- The design table
- The age analysis
- The SRT analysis
- The positive controls
- The analyses done at all SNRs of the psychometric
curves

(a) Design table

Table S-1 presents the design for the related paper. The
sampling plan column was removed so that the table was
more legible.

Table S - 1: Design table.

Question	Hypothesis	Analysis	Interpretation given different outcomes
Are HI listeners more affected by reverberation when it is applied only on speech?	1: the temporal smearing of the speech caused by reverberation impairs more HI listeners than NH listeners.	Repeated measures mixed design Bayesian ANOVA. Objective: determine whether HI listeners are more impaired by reverberation on speech, by studying the group x RT interaction.	If $BF > 3$ for the RT x group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis 1 and proceed with the post hoc tests. If $BF < 1/3$: there is evidence for the absence of a group x RT interaction. Hypothesis 1 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.
Are HI listeners more affected by reverberation when it is applied only on speech?	1-1: the temporal smearing of the target speech impairs intelligibility at lower levels of reverberation for HI listeners compared to NH listeners (that is to say HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at low RTs).	Bayesian t-tests to do pairwise comparisons between RT = 0 s and the other RTs for each group and noise condition. Objective: determine the lowest RT at which each group is first affected.	RT threshold: lowest RT for which there is proof for a score difference compared to the RT = 0.15 s condition. It will indicate that the listeners are affected by reverberation above this particular RT. If the HI group has a lower RT threshold than the NH group: we claim full support for 1-1. If the HI group has a higher BF than the NH group for the same RT threshold: we claim partial support for 1-1. If there is no RT threshold ($BF < 1/3$ for all comparisons): hypothesis 1-1 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$ before reaching a minimum RT threshold: nothing can be concluded.
Are HI listeners more affected by reverberation when it is applied only on speech?	1-2: at high levels of reverberation, HI listeners are more impaired than NH listeners by the temporal smearing of the speech (that is to say, HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at high RTs).	Bayesian t-test to compare the difference in intelligibility scores between RT = 0 s and RT = 1.5 s for both groups and noise conditions. Objective: determine whether HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at high RTs.	If there is a difference between the difference in intelligibility scores for both groups ($BF > 3$): we claim full support for 1-2. If $BF < 1/3$: the magnitude of the effect is similar for both groups. Hypothesis 1-2 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.

<p>Are HI listeners affected differently by reverberation when it is applied only to modulated noise?</p>	<p>2: reverberation affects the dip listening benefit more for NH listeners than for HI listeners.</p>	<p>Repeated measure mixed design Bayesian ANOVAs. Objective: determine whether both groups are affected differently by the dip listening decrease, by studying the group \times RT \times noise interaction.</p>	<p>If $BF > 3$ for the RT \times noise \times group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis 2 and proceed with the post hoc tests. If $BF < 3$: hypothesis 2 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.</p>
<p>Are HI and NH listeners affected differently by reverberation when it is applied to noise and speech?</p>	<p>3-1: the overall (monaural) effect of reverberation impairs HI listeners as much as NH listeners.</p>	<p>Repeated measure mixed design Bayesian ANOVA. Objective: determine whether HI listeners are more impaired by reverberation on speech and noise, by studying the RT \times group interaction.</p>	<p>If $BF < 1/3$ for the RT \times group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis 3-1. If $BF > 3$: hypothesis 3-1 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.</p>
<p>In the case of NH listeners, does the dip listening decrease have a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise?</p>	<p>3-2-a: In the case of NH listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise.</p>	<p>Repeated measure mixed design Bayesian ANOVA with the results of the NH listeners. Objective: determine whether the dip listening decrease is significant when reverberation is applied to speech and noise, by studying the RT \times noise interaction.</p>	<p>If $BF > 3$ for the RT \times group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis for 3-2-a. If $BF < 1/3$: hypothesis 3-2-a is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.</p>

<p>In the case of HI listeners, does the dip listening decrease have a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise?</p>	<p>3-2-b: In the case of HI listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise.</p>	<p>Repeated measure mixed design Bayesian ANOVA with the results of the HI listeners. Objective: determine whether the dip listening decrease is significant when reverberation is applied to speech and noise, by studying the RT x noise interaction.</p>	<p>If $BF > 3$ for the RT x group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis for 3-2-b. If $BF < 1/3$: hypothesis 3-2-b is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.</p>
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(b) Age analysis

To determine whether the results presented in the related article were affected by the significant age difference between the HI and NH listeners, the mean psychometric curves of the original study were determined with subgroups of 25 HI and 25 NH listeners significantly matched in age ($BF = 0.33$). The three main tests of the original study (that is to say, the three ANOVAs comparing the two monaural effects of reverberation separately and in combination for HI and NH listeners) were also done with the same age-matched subgroups. The mean psychometric curves can be found on Figures S-1 to S-3, while the results from the three tests can be found in Table S-2.

Overall it appears that most results are similar between the original groups and the age-matched subgroups. The only variation is the difference of the effect of reverberation on the dip listening benefit between the HI and NH listeners. In this case an interaction is detected at low SNRs for the original groups while the test is inconclusive for the age-matched groups. This difference could be due to the age difference, but also to the smaller number of listeners in the age-matched groups, which reduces the scale of the effects.

Figure S - 1. Mean psychometric curves of the age-matched HI and NH listeners when reverberation was applied only to the speech.

Figure S - 2. Mean psychometric curves of the HI and NH listeners when reverberation was applied only to the noise.

Figure S - 3. Mean psychometric curves of the HI and NH listeners when reverberation was applied to the speech and the noise.

Table S - 2: Age analyses

Hypothesis	Test	Result (original groups)	Result (age-matched groups)	Interpretation
1: The temporal smearing of the speech caused by reverberation impairs more HI listeners than NH listeners	Bayesian ANOVA (RT x group interaction) at the SNR with the least amount of floor and ceiling effects	BF = 0.03	BF = 0.02	In both cases (original groups and age-matched groups) the hypothesis is rejected.
2: Reverberation affects the dip listening benefit more for NH listeners than for HI listeners	Bayesian ANOVA (RT x noise type x group interaction) at the SNR with the least amount of floor and ceiling effects and the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit for the HI listeners	At the SNR with the least amount of floor and ceiling effects, BF=0.28 At the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit for the HI listeners, BF=3.1	At the SNR with the least amount of floor and ceiling effects, BF=0.28 At the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit for the HI listeners, BF=0.7	In both cases the hypothesis is rejected at the optimal SNR. However, at the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit for HI listeners, no conclusion is possible for the age-matched groups, while the hypothesis is accepted for the original groups.

<p>3-1: The overall (monaural) effect of reverberation impairs HI listeners as much as NH listeners</p>	<p>Bayesian ANOVA (RT x group interaction) at the SNR with the least amount of floor and ceiling effects and the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit for the HI listeners</p>	<p>At the SNR with the least amount of floor and ceiling effects, BF = 1.75 At the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit for the HI listeners, BF = $7 * 10^4$</p>	<p>At the SNR with the least amount of floor and ceiling effects, BF = 0.48 At the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit for the HI listeners, BF = 220</p>	<p>In both cases no conclusion is possible at the optimal SNR, and the hypothesis is accepted at the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit.</p>
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(c) SRT analysis

The main paper analysed the results by fitting psychometric curves on the listeners' scores and doing the tests at various SNRs. This method allows to avoid the confounding effect that the SNR has on the dip listening benefit, by analysing the results of HI and NH listeners at a common SNR. It also allows to have a broader view of the listeners' speech intelligibility by studying the entirety of the psychometric curve and not just a single point. It can also highlight potential floor and ceiling effects on the results. It was decided to do the same analyses as those from the main study with the SRTs of the listeners, in order to provide the community with an alternative view of the same data set to enable easy comparison with both previous and future experimental studies and models.

These SRTs were estimated from the fitted psychometric curves and can be found in Figures S-4, S-5 and S-6. The results of the statistical tests, can be found in Table S-3. Most of the tests are inconclusive when they are done on the SRTs. This is in accordance with the results obtained in the paper, which show that most of the differences between groups were only present in the lower and higher parts of the psychometric curves. The tests leading to conclusive results show that both groups experience a strong effect of reverberation when it is applied only to the speech (planned analysis 1-1) but only the NH listeners have a significant dip listening benefit (planned tests 3-2-a and 3-2-b). This most likely comes from the confounding effect of the SNR, with the HI listeners having higher SRTs, where the dip listening benefit is less important.

Figure S - 4. SRTs of the HI and NH listeners when reverberation is applied only to the speech.

Table S - 3: Analyses on the estimated SRTs

Hypothesis	Test	Result	Interpretation
1: The temporal smearing of the speech caused by reverberation impairs more HI listeners than NH listeners	ANOVA (RT × group interaction)	BF = 0.54	Inconclusive

1-1: The temporal smearing of the target speech impairs intelligibility at lower levels of reverberation for HI listeners compared to NH listeners	t-tests between RTs	BF > 10 for both groups at all RTs	The hypothesis is rejected.
1-2: At high levels of reverberation, HI listeners are more impaired than NH listeners by the temporal smearing of the speech (that is to say, HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at high RTs)	t-test to compare the score difference of the groups between RT = 0.15 s and RT = 1.5 s	BF = 9182	The hypothesis is accepted
The magnitude of the effect of reverberation on speech is higher for HI listeners at low RTs	t-tests to compare the difference in intelligibility scores between RT = 0 s and the intermediary RTs for both groups	BF > 10 at all RTs	The hypothesis is rejected.
2: Reverberation affects the dip listening benefit more for NH listeners than for HI listeners	ANOVA (RT x noise type x group interaction)	BF = 0.61	Inconclusive
There is a difference in dip listening benefit between groups	ANOVA (group x noise type interaction)	BF = 1.12	Inconclusive
3-1: The overall (monaural) effect of reverberation impairs HI listeners as much as NH listeners	ANOVA (RT x group interaction)	BF = 2.25	Inconclusive
3-2-a: In the case of NH listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise	ANOVA (RT x noise type interaction for the NH group)	BF = $1.2 * 10^6$	The hypothesis is accepted
3-2-b: In the case of HI listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise	ANOVA (RT x noise type interaction for the HI group)	BF = 0.65	Inconclusive

Figure S - 5. SRTs of the HI and NH listeners when reverberation is applied only to the noise.

Figure S - 6. SRTs of the HI and NH listeners when reverberation is applied to the speech and noise.

(d) Positive controls

Some positive controls were run to confirm the effects of the temporal smearing of the speech and the dip listening benefit. These results can be found in Table S-4. For both groups there was a strong effect of the temporal smearing of the speech. Both groups did not have a significant dip listening benefit at the optimal SNR with the minimum amount of floor and ceiling effects (-6.3 dB), only at the SNR with the maximum amount of dip listening benefit for the HI listeners (-10.3 dB).

Table S - 4: Positive controls

Hypothesis	Test	Result	Interpretation
Both groups experience a significant effect of the temporal smearing of the speech by reverberation	ANOVA (main effect of RT for each group)	BF = 10^{31} for the HI and BF = 10^{45} for the NH listeners.	The hypothesis is accepted.
Each group experience a dip listening benefit when reverberation is applied only to the noise.	ANOVA (main effect of masker type for each group)	At -6.3 dB, BF = 0.25 for HI listeners and BF = 0.51 for NH listeners. At -10.3 dB, BF = 5.51 for the HI listeners and BF = $3 * 10^6$ for the NH listeners.	The hypothesis is rejected at -6.3 dB but accepted at -10.3 dB.
Each group experience a decrease in dip listening benefit due to reverberation applied on the noise masker.	ANOVA (RT x masker type for each group)	At -6.3 dB, BF = 0.7 for HI listeners and BF = 1.89 for NH listeners. At -10.3 dB, BF = 3.3 for the HI listeners and BF = $3 * 10^6$ for the NH listeners.	The hypothesis is rejected at -6.3 dB but accepted at -10.3 dB.
There is a significant effect of reverberation applied on speech and noise for both groups.	ANOVA (main effect of RT for each group)	BF = $2 * 10^{25}$ for the HI and BF = $1 * 10^{44}$ for the NH listeners.	The hypothesis is accepted for both groups.

(e) Analysis done at all SNRs

In order to have a broader view of the studied effects, all the tests of the main study were also done at all the SNRs. These results can be found in Figures S-7 to S-16. As expected, the presence of floor and ceiling effects affected the results (i.e. for example, we do not expect any differences across groups or conditions when all the participants reach the floor or, conversely, when they reach the ceiling), and the Bayes factors are color-coded on the plots presenting the corresponding percent of floor and ceiling effects. A summary of these results can also be found in Table S-6.

The Bayes Factor studying hypothesis 1 (Fig S-7) found a more important score impairment due to the temporal smearing of the speech for HI listeners for SNRs above 1 dB. The effect of reverberation was the same between the groups for SNRs below -20 dB and between -7 dB and -1 dB. The additional t-tests comparing the score differences between groups (Fig S-8, S-9, S-10 and S-11) found a significant difference at RT = 0.5 s for SNRs below -11 dB and above -3 dB, while it was significant for SNRs below -7 dB and above -1 dB for RT = 0.8 s, RT = 1.1 s, and RT = 1.5 s. Overall, most differences between groups happened above the optimal SNR. This might imply that the temporal smearing of the speech has a different effect between groups at lower noise sound levels, but is most likely due to ceiling effects.

The dip listening reduction caused by reverberation (Fig. S-12) was found significantly different for HI and NH listeners below -11 dB, while it was the same for both groups between -7 dB and -4 dB and above -1 dB. The results were similar for the difference of dip listening between groups (Fig. S-13), except for SNRs between -4 dB and -1 dB. Overall, most of the differences between groups happened at low SNRs. This is expected, since the dip listening benefit is only present at low SNRs. These differences could imply a lower dip listening benefit for the HI listeners, as well as a reduced effect of reverberation on the dip listening benefit. They could also be due to floor effects.

When reverberation was applied to speech and noise, there was a significant difference of effect of reverberation between the groups for SNRs below -6 dB and above 0 dB and no difference for SNRs between -3 and -2 dB (Fig S-14). For the HI listeners, the dip listening reduction caused by reverberation was significantly present at SNRs between -9 dB and -17 dB and significantly absent above -3 dB (Fig S-15). For the NH listeners, the dip listening reduction caused by reverberation was significantly present at SNRs below -6 dB and significantly absent above -3 dB (Fig S-16).

These results show that most of the differences between groups happened at SNRs with floor and ceiling effects. These differences usually decrease and/or become significantly absent around the optimal SNR. This could imply that the significant effects that appear at these SNRs are at least partly due to those floor and ceiling effects.

Table S - 5: Summary of the results of the analyses done at all SNRs

Hypothesis	Test	Result	Interpretation
The temporal smearing of the speech caused by reverberation impairs more HI listeners than NH listeners	ANOVA (RT x group interaction).	BF < 1/3 for SNRs between -5 dB and -2 dB, BF > 3 for SNRs above 0 dB	For SNRs between -5 dB and -2 dB the hypothesis is rejected, but for SNRs above 0 dB the hypothesis is accepted.

<p>The magnitude of the effect of reverberation on speech is higher for HI listeners only at low RTs.</p>	<p>t-tests to compare the difference in intelligibility scores between RT = 0 s and the intermediary RTs (0.5 s, 0.8 s, 1.1 s) for both groups</p>	<p>At RT = 0.5 s , BF > 3 for SNRs below -11 dB and above -3 dB, At RT = 0.8 s and RT = 1.1 s s, BF > 3 for SNRs below -7 dB and above -1 dB</p>	<p>At RT = 0.5 s ,the hypothesis is accepted for SNRs below -11 dB and above -3 dB , At RT = 0.8 s and RT = 1.1 s s, the hypothesis is accepted for SNRs below -7 dB and above -1 dB</p>
<p>At high levels of reverberation, HI listeners are more impaired than NH listeners by the temporal smearing of the speech (that is to say, HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at high RTs).</p>	<p>t-test to compare the score difference of the groups between RT = 0.15 s and RT = 1.5 s</p>	<p>BF > 3 for SNRs below -7 dB and above -1 dB, and BF < 1/3 for SNRs between -4 dB and -3 dB</p>	<p>For SNRs below -7 dB and above -1 dB the hypothesis is accepted. For SNRs between -4 dB and -3 dB the hypothesis is rejected.</p>
<p>Reverberation affects the dip listening benefit more for NH listeners than for HI listeners.</p>	<p>ANOVA (RT x noise x group interaction)</p>	<p>BF > 3 for SNRs below -11 dB, BF < 1/3 for SNRs between -7 dB and -4 dB and above -1 dB</p>	<p>For SNRs below -11 dB, the hypothesis is accepted. For SNRs between -7 dB and -4 dB and above -1 dB, the hypothesis is rejected.</p>
<p>The NH benefit more from the dip listening benefit than the HI listeners.</p>	<p>ANOVA (noise x group interaction)</p>	<p>BF > 3 for SNRs below -11 dB, BF < 1/3 for SNRs above -7 dB</p>	<p>For SNRs below -11 dB, the hypothesis is accepted. For SNRs above -7 dB, the hypothesis is rejected.</p>
<p>The overall (monaural) effect of reverberation impairs HI listeners as much as NH listeners.</p>	<p>ANOVA (RT x group interaction)</p>	<p>BF > 3 for SNRs below -6 dB and above 0 dB and BF < 1/3 for SNRs between -3 and -2 dB</p>	<p>For SNRs below -6 dB and above 0 dB the hypothesis is accepted. For SNRs between -3 and -2 dB the hypothesis is rejected.</p>
<p>In the case of NH listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise.</p>	<p>ANOVA (RT x noise interaction for the NH group)</p>	<p>BF > 3 for SNRs below -6 dB and BF < 1/3 for SNRs above -3 dB</p>	<p>For SNRs below -6 dB the hypothesis is accepted. For SNRs above -3 dB, the hypothesis is rejected.</p>

<p>In the case of HI listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise.</p>	<p>ANOVA (RT x noise interaction for the HI group)</p>	<p>BF > 3 for SNRs between -9 dB and -17 dB and BF < 1/3 for SNRs above -3 dB</p>	<p>For SNRs between -9 dB and -17 dB the hypothesis is accepted. For SNRs above -3 dB the hypothesis is rejected.</p>
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Figure S - 7. Upper panel: Bayes Factor comparing the effect of reverberation on speech between groups, depending on the SNR. Lower panel: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor (>15%) and ceiling (<95%) values. The colored hatches indicate the area with significant effect (red), significant lack of effect (green) and inconclusive results (blue).

Figure S - 8. Upper graph: Bayes Factor comparing the score differences of NH and HI listeners, between RTs of 0.15 s and 0.5 s, depending on the SNRs. Lower Graph: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values.

Figure S - 9. Upper graph: Bayes Factor comparing the score differences of NH and HI listeners, between RTs of 0.15 s and 0.8 s, depending on the SNRs. Lower Graph: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values.

Figure S - 10. Upper graph: Bayes Factor comparing the score differences of NH and HI listeners, between RTs of 0.15 s and 1.1 s, depending on the SNRs. Lower Graph: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values.

Figure S - 11. Upper graph: Bayes Factor comparing the score differences of NH and HI listeners, between RTs of 0.15 s and 1.5 s, depending on the SNRs. Lower Graph: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values.

Figure S - 12. Upper graph: Bayes Factor studying the difference of dip listening reduction caused by reverberation between HI and NH listeners, depending on the SNR. Lower Graph: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values, with color hatches indicating the results obtained.

Figure S - 13. Upper graph: Bayes Factor studying the difference of dip listening benefit between HI and NH listeners, depending on the SNR. Lower Graph: percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values, with color hatches indicating the results obtained.

Figure S - 14. Upper graph: Bayes Factors comparing the effect of reverberation on speech and noise between groups, depending on the SNR. Lower Graph: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values, with color hatches indicating the results obtained.

Figure S - 15. Upper graph: Bayes Factor studying the dip listening reduction caused by reverberation (when applied to both speech and noise) for HI listeners, depending on the SNRs. Lower Graph: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values.

Figure S - 16. Upper graph: Bayes Factor studying the dip listening reduction caused by reverberation (when applied to both speech and noise) for NH listeners, depending on the SNRs. Lower Graph: Percentage of conditions within the limit floor and ceiling values.